

MLentory Technical Design Document

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Acronyms

TDD - Technical Design Document

ML - Machine Learning

NFDI4DS- National Research Data Infrastructure for Data Science

ETL - Extract Transform Load

ELT - Extract Load Transform

RDF - Resource Description Framework

MVP - Minimum Viable Product

HF - Hugging Face

CI - Continuous integration

CD - Continuous development

Version

- 1.0 Initial version for the architecture for the first 3 months plan - 12/02/2024
- 1.1 Updated version for publication - 26/05/2025

Purpose

To build a system that extracts ML model information from different platforms normalizes that data in a common format, stores it, and shares it in a FAIR Digital Object (FDO) registry to facilitate information retrieval (IR) and comparison/recommendation systems.

This TDD will help new contributors understand and old ones remember what decisions were made on the system's design, the motivation behind them, and their impact. The document focuses on the design of the ETL pipeline to collect, transform, and store extracted information.

Background

This project is part of the NFDI4DataScience initiative, a German Consortium whose vision is to support all steps of the complex and interdisciplinary research data lifecycle, including collecting/creating, processing, analyzing, publishing, archiving, and reusing resources in Data Science and Artificial Intelligence [16]. Our project, namely MLentory, is centered around information on ML models, how to harmonize that data, and how to make it available and searchable on an FDO registry.

Figure 1. General diagram of the NFDI4DataScience main project. Internal NFDI4DS diagram.

A big effort in this project will be using semantic technologies aligned to the FDO concept, so information from various ML model platforms is stored using a common data structure, easy for semantic purposes but also optimized for IR.

In the end, the system and the data it collects will help researchers and other interested parties to easily find and compare ML models from different platforms.

Requirements

Functional requirements

- F1. The system collects raw data describing ML models from different web platforms.
- F2. The system processes data describing ML models in different formats to identify and store relevant information about each model.
- F3. The system implements robust techniques to ensure data integrity.
- F4. The system provides data transformation and normalization mechanisms to ensure consistency in the data extracted from different platforms using a common data structure.
- F5. The system can adjust to minor changes in the data structure schema.
- F6. The system stores the normalized data in a semantic-compatible database.
- F7. The system supports versioning to track changes and updates to information on registered ML models over time.
- F8. The system can monitor and log system activities, errors, and performance metrics.

Non Functional requirements

- NF1. The system is maintainable.
 - NF1.a. The system is modular, allowing for easy integration of new functionalities or components.
 - NF1.b. The system is interoperable; it is easy to integrate outside platforms and systems.
 - NF1.c. The system is testable, allowing us to identify and fix issues when modifications are made.
- NF2. The system is scalable.
 - NF2.a. The system can scale processing power horizontally and vertically.
 - NF2.b. The system can scale storage capacity.
- NF3. The system stores the normalized data using a semantic format.
- NF4. The system extracts metadata from every source on a regular basis.
- NF5. The system has clear documentation for users and developers.
- NF6. The system is built using tools and strategies familiar to the development team as much as possible.

Detailed design

ETL pipeline design:

The developer must consider several elements when designing ETL pipelines. First, we must consider how to approach each pipeline's three steps: extract, transform, and load. Then, we will make decisions regarding the process as a whole.

New contributors can find the resources on which we base this section in [2],[3],[5],[6],[9],[10],[12],[13],[14],[15].

Figure 2. Diagram of ETL process. Source: [9]

Extract stage

The Extract stage of the ETL process involves collecting structured and unstructured data from its data sources. This stage will ultimately consolidate the data in a single registry. The data extraction part of the ETL process poses several challenges. For this system, we will collect metadata from various ML model repositories including Hugging Face (HF), Space ML, Radiant, MLHub, MODEL HUB, AI4Life, Kipoi, OpenML, and KLHub. The inclusion of each resource and additions to the list, will be considered on an individual basis, depending on technical issues (e.g., availability of an API or a data dump) and others as needed (e.g., licensing). The idea is to integrate the sources individually, starting with the HF platform as it is one of the more popular nowadays. The idea is to build a solid and complete Minimum Viable Product (MVP) that works as a base for new functionalities and improvements. To facilitate the development of the MVP, we will start with one platform.

Here are some of the challenges identified and our considerations about them:

- Data latency (How fast do we need the data?):

The definitive estimate will vary based on how expensive and time-consuming it is to bring data from different sources. Still, updates scheduled between a week and a month apart are a good estimate. Ideally, the system would update the information instantaneously to provide information on every available model at any time. In reality, the data sources we will be working with do not necessarily have webhooks

that can update us on such events. Even if they had them, these webhooks are usually unreliable.

- Data volume:

We base the following calculations on the HF platform. As of 2024.01.30, there are currently 481,801 models. The average metadata file is between 2 kB and 10 kB, which means there will be around 1 GB to 4.8 GB of (meta)data in HF ML models. The system will have to store at least 5 GB of data, which indicates that the requirements for data storage are rather low and not a crucial consideration. We will perform similar calculations for each of the remaining data sources, but data storage will most likely not become a problem for the system in general.

- Source limits:

For the HF platform, we know that the free Inference API may be rate-limited for heavy use cases. They try to balance the loads evenly between all our available resources. If the account suddenly sends 10k requests, it will likely receive 503 errors saying models are loading. We need to start running queries smoothly from 0 to 10k over a few minutes to prevent that.

Assuming 3 minutes per 10K requests, it will take 481 minutes or one day to process all the models in HF if no parallelization technique is used. These restrictions severely limit the data ingestion process. Each platform will have a similar analysis.

- Disparate sources:

Working with data from different sources causes overhead and management problems. Before passing all the information to the Transform step, we can mitigate these problems with the data in a unified column format, e.g., CSV.

Taking the previous considerations into account, the structure of the extract module would look as follows:

Figure 3. Deployment Diagram of the Extract section in the ETL process.

We convey the following decisions in Figure 3:

- The **Metadata Extractor** component is another abstraction that encapsulates the logic of transforming the unstructured or semistructured data received from the platforms into a structured data format. This can range from parsing a JSON object to identifying metadata fields in plain text files. It is important to mention that no significant data cleaning will be done in this step, this is to be expected from the transform part of the pipeline.
- Using a **Kafka server**, the system will transfer the extracted data from all the different platforms to the next stages. The server will work to provide queues to communicate the extraction and transformation stage, as well as the transformation and Loading stage. Having the data from all the different platforms in an intermediate standard format can help speed up and decouple the transformation stage of the pipeline.
- The format shared across components, which will be in JSON format, will have its fields defined based on the Metadata Schema defined for the project. We will discuss the data schema further in the Transform stage.

The data extracted from each of those platforms will be an answer to at least one of the questions in Table 1.

What is the name of the model?
Who created/uploaded the model?
When was the model created/uploaded?
What tasks can the model solve?
What datasets was the model trained on?
What was the split distribution for the datasets?
What datasets were used to finetune the model?
What datasets were used to retrain the model?
What model is used as the base model?
What evaluation metrics were used?
What were the values of the evaluation metrics?
What hyperparameters were optimized during the training process?
What hyperparameters were selected?
What publications are related to the model?
Where is the model deployed?
What use license is associated with the model?

Table 1. Questions needed to be answered by metadata.

Answering those questions is the basis for building the database, using as a starting point a schema as described in Figure 4. This schema is based on schema.org, which has been selected due to its flexibility and familiarity of the team with it (i.e., previous work with [Bioschemas](#) and [machine-actionable Software Management Plans](#)) as well as its current use to represent scientific artifacts (e.g., [Bioschemas](#), [Data Discovery Engine](#), [Science on Schema](#), [ML Commons Croissant](#), [CodeMeta](#)). The schema depicted in Figure 4 corresponds to a beta version so changes are expected. Such changes will align (as needed) to the work done in the Research Data Alliance (RDA) [FAIR4ML Interest Group](#) and later to the NFDI4DataScience controlled vocabulary. This will facilitate interoperability with other systems on ML models and, in general, related research artifacts.

Draft BETA Metadata Schema proposed by ZB MED

To be presented and discussed with NFDI4DS, ELIXIR ML, RDA FAIR4ML
 Prepared by Leyla Jael Castro, Dhvani Solanki, Dietrich Rebbholz-Schuhmann

Figure 4. BETA version of a schema.org-based proposal for ML models by ZB MED.

Data extraction for the HF Platform

The data corresponding to HF models is stored in a README.md file in markdown format. To obtain those files, we use the HF API that can be accessed (or data dumps for the initial extraction), for most functionalities, using a Python library and making queries directly to it. There is a limit of 10K requests that can be made in under 3 minutes, and there is also a limit on the amount of information that can be downloaded in a specific time frame. The limit on the amount of information that can be downloaded is not disclosed by them and fluctuates.

Once you can access the README.md file, there are still some difficulties in the data extraction process:

- The files can be written in different languages (English, French, Chinese, etc). At the beginning, we will only process files in English.
- The file structure can change drastically between different models. There is a default template that is suggested, but not everybody uses it.
- The files contain different amounts of information. Even if the default template is used, some sections are written in different styles, which implies they contain different information, and other sections are not written at all.

Writing a standard script that can handle all the different types of file structures and content is challenging as it will be able to cover some common cases but can miss others. Combining a direct extraction with ML approaches would allow us to cover a broader spectrum. The model will learn the patterns and structures of the README.md files and extract the relevant metadata information from them. The initial focus will be on direct extraction, even if most of the information is then stored as plain text. Whenever a task does not need the development of a new learning process, it will be considered for the MVP and initial stages.

The problem of data extraction is a more noble one for which there is not a plug-and-play solution already built. So first, what task will the model solve to extract the metadata from the README.md files? There are 2 alternatives:

- **Question Answering (QA):** Focuses on answering specific questions formulated in natural language. The idea is to model the relationship between a question and its corresponding answer within a context. Well-suited for scenarios where you want to extract answers to specific predefined questions from the text.
- **Named Entity Recognition (NER):** Focuses on identifying and categorizing specific predefined entity types within the text. Examples of entity types: people, locations, organizations, dates, currencies, etc. Useful for extracting specific types of information regardless of a specific question, allowing a broader exploration of the text.

These approaches will be implemented in the later stages of the project, for now, we will focus on extracting the data that is already in a suitable format.

To start, we are using the dataset found in [26] to make the first big dump upload of metadata to the system. After that periodic updates will be done using the HuggingFace Hub API.

Transform stage

In this stage of the ETL process, the data collected at the extractor stage is changed/transformed before being saved in the final database. The idea is to receive the data in the CSV files from the Extract step and perform the transformations necessary to clean and normalize the data. Here are some of the considerations for the transformation step:

- Data cleaning

We need to pay particular attention to the following steps for our use case:

- Recode missing data into NULLs, 0, or #NA, based on the nature of the field.
- Recode different versions of the same data to a common denominator. For example, "M", "1", "male", and "masculine" to "Male. " Another example is having different platforms with different names for the same metric.
- Unify data types to standard forms. For example, convert DateTime objects and Unix timestamps to the same data type.

- Data validation

It is important to ensure that the data from each field has the correct data type and, if possible, check that the values make sense in the field context. If a field representing the value of an Evaluation metric has letters, it is important to check whether those letters make sense in that context, like "1e14", or they are just errors in the extraction process, like "asdf123".

- Shifts in data sources

Data sources can change the data they provide or the process to get it. Here is where the decoupling logic of the extraction step comes in handy. When the data reaches the transform step, it is already in a defined column format. The source of the information or the amount of it provided is transparent to the Transform step. Furthermore, if one of the extraction modules fails because of changes in the extraction process, that does not affect the other extraction modules or the rest of the pipeline.

The idea is to have a Scheduler activate the Transformation pipeline at set time intervals. A week will suffice in this example, but it could be every day or hour. It is important to notice that the intervals in which the data is extracted from the platforms and when it is transformed do not have to match. Data from platforms can take days to be completely extracted, and we do not need to wait for all the data to be extracted to start transforming it, thus speeding up the process.

Figure 5. Sequence Diagram of the Transform section in the ETL process.

The diagram conveys another idea to speed things up. Using multi-threading to process the files is a simple idea that must not be overlooked in the implementation process. It can bring computational efficiency to the process.

Figure 4 shows an initial version of the metadata schema proposed for ML models. The idea is to normalize all the metadata collected in this shared format. This format should be semantically significant to enable users and computer systems to discover, compare, and understand ML models more easily.

Load stage

Load involves taking data from the transform stage and saving it to a target database, where it is ready to be consumed by other services to perform analysis on it or be served in a Frontend.

- Updating Uploaded Metadata

This can become a tricky task; first, we need to identify if there is a need to replace an old fact or if it is a new fact about the ML model; in case we need to replace an old fact, we need to figure out what to do with the fact that is being replaced. Here are some options for the second problem:

- Delete and Insert:
 - This is the simplest approach: delete the old statement and insert the new one.
 - Pros: Easy to implement, clear separation of past and present information.
 - Cons: Loss of history, no explicit indication that the statement has changed.
- Named Graphs:
 - Assign each statement to a named graph identifying its validity period (e.g., "statements-2024-02-07").
 - Pros: Preserves historical data and allows querying based on specific timeframes.
 - Cons: Can increase complexity and requires additional management of named graphs.
- Introduce Metadata about the current version:
 - Add a property to the statement indicating its validity period (e.g., "validFrom", "validTo").
 - Pros: Flexible, customizable, avoids data duplication.
 - Cons: It requires querying based on this metadata, a potential performance overhead.

Introducing metadata is the best option for our situation. This method incurs some performance and storage issues as mentioned before. Having metadata for each triplet would imply that every time we modify or update a triplet, we would have to store this metadata as if it were a new triplet. Thus we decided to store data in different formats to make storing and retrieving data more efficient.

- Database

With the introduction of data in the previous point, we can consider what other types of information we want to keep track of, like:

- The last time a statement in a model was modified. We can track it using the "validFrom" and "validTo" statements.
- The data source that provided the statement.
- Information on how the data was collected from the data source.

Those fields can help us assess data credibility, identify potential biases, and trace changes to specific actors. The diagram in Figure 6 shows that the metadata concerns are being addressed.

Figure 6 SQL diagram to keep track of triplets and their metadata.

The next question is: How do we make the information stored using the previous data schema queryable? This is a concern because the data schema described in Figure 6 was not built to find information about the models in an efficient manner; it was designed to store the triplet metadata information in a compact manner that allows for reconstructing the model data in any particular time frame. For that reason, we opted to use two more systems to store the models' data, the first one being an RDF database that is optimized to store graph data and do queries over it, and the second being Elasticsearch an indexing system that allows you to make natural language.

The following is a sequence diagram where the concerns previously mentioned are taken care of:

Figure 7 Sequence Diagram of the Load section in the ETL process.

The process starts by **loading a file** containing the new triplets, with their respective metadata, about the models that have been extracted and transformed. This information could include triplets from a new model or triplets meant to update an existing model. So the next step is to identify which case it is, in order to do so we try to **get related triplets** to the model, If we don't find any information about this model, it means is brand new, otherwise this model already existed and we need to modify the current triplets based on that, during this process we **identify the outdated triplets**. To make this step faster, and to not use so much space, we design the data schema in Figure 6 that will allow us to identify if a triplet is old or new and keep track of its lifecycle. After that, it is a matter of **adding the new triplets** and **deprecating**, not deleting, the old ones. The idea is to keep track of how the models have evolved over time, and the SQL database allows us to do that.

Our last two steps involve keeping just the current version of the models' metadata in an RDF database and indexing that information in Elasticsearch. Adding this information to these two different systems will allow us to query the models' information more dynamically and efficiently. Graph queries in SPARQL format for RDF, and natural text search queries for Elasticsearch. The previous functionalities are not easily achieved by just using the SQL database.

General Considerations

In this section, some transversal concerns about the whole pipeline are discussed.

- Pipeline extraction pattern:

ETL Pipelines gather and process data differently based on business concerns and priorities. Some pipelines gather data as soon as it is generated, called Streaming pipelines. Other pipelines periodically gather information, called Batched pipelines. And there are other characterizations in between that use a combination of both in different proportions.

During the discussion so far, we have expressed that the Batched approach is more suitable for our System. The pros of this approach are a good balance between data freshness and computational resources needed; the infrastructure providing batched data tends to be less fragile and more reliable; and our data sources don't have any streaming capabilities. The cons come from the possibility of missing updates on the data and not being able to bring the freshest results every time.

- Monitoring:

You need to monitor your extraction system on several levels:

- Resources. How much computational power and memory is being allocated?

Based on first impressions, this project shouldn't be particularly computationally expensive. Still, we would like to implement railways that allow us to track how many resources the system is consuming, such that when we integrate new extraction platforms or functionalities, we don't overload the server.

- Errors. Have any errors caused missing or corrupted data?

These problems can occur during the Extraction or Transformation stages, so it is crucial to keep track of the health of the data. We can do this by implementing tests after each step of the ETL pipeline.

- Reliability. Have the extraction scripts run at all?

This type of question can help us identify situations where the data sources have changed and the respective extractor module stops working. Using the proper orchestration and deployment tools, we can overcome this issue.

- **Orchestration:**

The best way to reduce errors, save time, and overcome the challenges of the ETL process is to automate all the steps. One way of achieving this is by using orchestration tools. Based on time constraints, state of the system, and other external signals, these tools can trigger the data extraction, transformation, and loading pipelines.

Effective orchestration can help us run the pipeline smoothly, efficiently, and with minimal manual intervention. It also helps quickly diagnose and resolve any issues that arise.

- **Deployment:**

Containerization tools like Docker offer a solution by packaging each data process into an isolated container with all its dependencies and libraries. The use of containerization eliminates environment-specific conflicts and streamlines deployments. As the container orchestrator, Kubernetes seamlessly scales the pipeline based on workload, spinning up additional container instances only when required. Furthermore, Kubernetes facilitates independent container restarts, ensuring that even individual platform failures don't affect the entire pipeline.

Figure 8. Deployment Diagram of the whole ETL pipeline.

The transformation and the loading process basically perform the same operations in different threads, so there is no need to have multiple containers to handle these processes. If reliability in the data processing was a deep concern, meaning we had to minimize downtime, we could consider using replicas of that container, but that is not our case.

The data quality checker module will generate metrics on the data quality, such as the percentage of null fields per model, platform, and batch, as well as basic validations on the data fields like data format, data types, ranges validations, and many others.

Tools

Here is a discussion of what tools will be used to implement the previous designs. The resources on which this section is based can be found in [1],[4],[7],[8],[11],[17],[18],[19],[20] and [22].

Programming Language

The selected programming language to develop the project is Python for the following reasons:

- **Ease of Use:** Python is known for its simplicity and readability, making it easy for developers to write, understand, and maintain code for ETL tasks. Its syntax resembles pseudo-code, which makes it accessible even to those with little programming experience. Most ZB Med semantic technologies team members know how to use Python, making the learning curve to contribute to the project way smaller.
- **Abundance of Libraries:** Python boasts a vast ecosystem of libraries and frameworks specifically designed for data manipulation and ETL tasks. Libraries such as Pandas, NumPy, and SQLAlchemy provide powerful tools for data processing, transformation, and interaction with various data sources.
- **Integration Capabilities:** Python seamlessly integrates with many databases, file formats, and APIs, making it suitable for extracting data from diverse sources.
- **Scalability:** While Python is often chosen for its ease of use and rapid development capabilities, it can also handle large-scale ETL processes.

Even if **performance** and **memory usage** are real concerns when using Python, there are many ways to circumvent these issues, such as libraries like NumPy and Pandas, that help to optimize performance for many common data manipulation tasks or using orchestration and deployment tools to scale processes horizontally. Now, problems like **dependency management**, **debugging**, and **error handling** are concerns the developer has to get used to, as they are part of Python's nature.

Another worthy mention was the GO programming language for the following reasons:

- **Performance and Efficiency:** GO is a compiled language known for its speed and efficient memory management. This makes it ideal for handling large datasets and complex transformations without sacrificing performance, especially when compared to Python.
- **Native Parallelization:** GO excels at handling concurrency and parallelism through its lightweight goroutines and channels. This enables the efficient distribution of tasks across multiple CPU cores, significantly speeding up data processing compared to Python's Global Interpreter Lock (GIL), which limits true parallelism.
- **Static Typing and Reliability:** GO is statically typed, which helps catch errors early in the development process and leads to more robust and maintainable code compared to dynamic languages like Python. This can be crucial for mission-critical ETL pipelines where data integrity is paramount.

However, there are some important concerns to keep in mind; GO would add a **bigger learning curve** for the team members and thus increase the time in which contributions could be made to the system. The **libraries** in the programming language are not as mature as they are in Python, increasing the chances of running into unexpected problems. Finally, the **community** is not as big as Python's community, so if a problem is found, it is less likely to have a documented solution for it. These concerns this time around were too big to ignore.

Even though it does not look like a feasible option right now, if the system were to need a speed up in performance, the modular nature of the architecture would allow us to interchange parts of the system, like the Transform stage, into a different programming language without too much trouble.

Version Control Tools

We will use Git as the version control protocol and Github as the platform where all the data will be stored. Together, Git and GitHub provide a powerful and versatile solution for version control.

Git Key Advantages:

- **Distributed Version Control:** Git offers a complete copy of your project history on every developer's machine. This allows for:
 - Offline work
 - Decentralized development
 - Increased resilience
- **Efficient Branching and Merging:** Git excels at creating isolated branches for experimenting or fixing bugs without affecting the main codebase. Merging these branches back into the main code is streamlined and intuitive.

- **Clear History Tracking:** You can see exactly what changes were made, by whom, and when.
- **Lightweight and Efficient:** Git only stores differences between versions, making it efficient for large projects and minimizing storage requirements.
- **Extensive Community and Ecosystem**

GitHub Advantages:

- **Code hosting and collaboration platform:** GitHub provides a user-friendly interface for hosting code repositories.
- **Version control visualization**
- **Issue tracking and project management**
- **Community and social features**

Database Tools

Going back to the loading diagram in Figure 7 we

Deployment Tools

Traditional deployments usually involve manual configuration, environment inconsistencies, and challenging scaling. Containerization tackles these issues, it helps to nicely package applications with all their dependencies into isolated units, ensuring identical behavior across any runtime environment. Containerization orchestration tools build on top of this by automating deployments and managing infrastructure as code, resulting in features like automatic scaling, health checks, and self-healing.

- **Docker**, as a containerization tool, remains relevant to most container projects, applications, and developers today thanks to its modern tools, compatibility, large community, and ease of use. Even if there are alternatives that offer extra features or focus on specific concerns like security, like rkt, or low-level control, like LXC/LXD, they don't offer a good enough argument to be implemented over Docker.
- **Kubernetes**, as a container orchestration tool, has several weak points, such as a big learning curve, potential performance overhead when handling a large number of containers, and security considerations, just to name the most important to us. The fact remains that its strong points are compelling to our use case: horizontal scaling, automated deployments, health checks, version control for infrastructure, large and active community, and a great number of integrations with open-source tools, libraries, and cloud providers' infrastructure. Some alternatives alleviate some of Kubernetes' problems, but definitively, they do not offer all of its strong points.

Continuous Integration and Deployment

We want to build a CI/CD component to identify bugs or manual deployment errors early and fast by automating tasks like building, testing, and deployment. This will allow us to deliver features faster, incorporate user feedback quicker, and iterate more efficiently.

Some considerations to select the right CI/CD tool for our team are that our development team will be small for the majority of the project, the data validation and component integration tests are not that complex, and we want to minimize the learning curve for new members as much as possible. Here we provide a list of some of the alternatives that are free or have free tier option:

- **Jenkins** is highly customizable, it has a vast plugin library, furthermore is free and open-source. Its drawbacks are that it requires a significant setup and maintenance, it is complex for beginners therefore has a big learning curve.
- **GitHub Actions** integrates seamlessly with GitHub workflows, easy to learn. But, it has limited features compared to Jenkins, and might not be suitable for complex projects. It offers 2,000 build minutes and 500 MB of memory for free and after any of those limits are crossed they start billing accordingly.

- **CircleCI** has a user-friendly interface, has a small learning curve, and integrates with various third-party providers easily. On the other side, it can become expensive for large teams, it has limited customization compared to Jenkins. For free you can have up to 6,000 build minutes and 5 active users per month.

Initially, we will use **CircleCI**. It offers similar features to GitHub Actions but with a more generous free tier. This lets us experiment with CI/CD without initial cost. If the free tier becomes limiting, we'll assess our resource consumption in CircleCI. Then, we can compare the paid plans of CircleCI and GitHub Actions to see if the extra features we need fit our budget. If neither paid option works, we'll invest time in learning Jenkins, acknowledging its increased complexity.

The idea is to trigger the CI/CD pipeline after every commit. Ideally, we will develop one big feature at a time. While developing a big feature, the necessary unit tests for it will be created as well and ensured to be passed by the developer in charge of the feature. When everything works fine for that particular feature, a pull request will be made and the CI/CD pipeline will focus on ensuring that the whole system keeps working reliably with the addition of the new code in the base source code. If testing the project becomes too computationally expensive we will have to move the the pipeline trigger to every pull request, for now testing every commit is fine.

During the CI process, we want to check for code being formatted the right way, we want to check for tests being passed, and for the test coverage to be at least 80%.

Orchestration Tools

These are tools that allow for the management and coordination of multiple tasks to execute a more extensive workflow or process. Here are some of the options that are compatible with Python:

- **Apache Airflow:**
 - Highly popular and mature open-source solution.
 - Extensible plugin architecture and flexible scheduling options.
 - Scalable but can have a steeper learning curve and potential configuration complexities.
- **Luigi:**
 - Developed by Spotify, focused on complex batch jobs.
 - Pythonic code style, clear data dependencies, and easy testing.
 - Might not be ideal for highly parallelized workflows or complex scheduling.
- **Dagster:**
 - Designed for flexibility and data-driven workflows.

- Modular architecture, pluggable ops, and support for data quality metrics.
- It has integrated tests to test and monitor data quality after each step.
- Relatively new but gaining traction for its user-friendliness.
- **Prefect:**
 - Modern, cloud-native approach with a simple syntax.
 - Built-in error handling and retry mechanisms.
 - Can be resource-intensive for large workflows.

From the above options, the two that stood out were Apache Airflow and Dagster. For us, Apache Airflow's strong points are a massive amount of existing code already built on it and a big community, which implies that there are plenty of solutions already built and documented and a lot of support for error handling. But, compared with Dagster, it lacks several important aspects:

- Data pipelines written for Airflow are typically bound to a particular environment, and testing before releasing to production tends to be quite complicated. Dagster makes it easy to alter the behavior of your pipelines based on their environment. A pipeline can write DataFrames to memory when executing within a unit test and store them in Snowflake when executing in production.
- The huge innovation Dagster has introduced is leveraging containerization to solve the Airflow monolith dependency issue entirely at the architectural level.
- Apache Airflow is task-focused rather than asset-focused: you define tasks and tell it to run them at particular times rather than declaring data assets that you want to keep up-to-date. Dagster the following questions easily: Is this asset up-to-date? What do I need to run to refresh this asset? When will this asset be updated next? What code and data were used to generate this asset?
- On the UI side, Dagster benefits from being built in the 2020s. Several users complain about Airflow's clunky interface and their struggles with monitoring and troubleshooting DAGs as a challenge. These issues are resolved in Dagster.

Figure 9. Airflow's web-based UI (Graph View). Source: Airflow

Figure 10. Dagster's web-based UI (Graph View) Source: Dagster.

One of the most notable drawbacks for Dagster is its growing community. Compared to the matured and established Airflows community, as of February of 2024, there were 10.465 questions about airflow in Stackoverflow, compared to the 170 questions of Dagster. Another concern is that its web interface does not come with authentication at all in the OSS version, but that is not a concern for us because to access the machines where this process will be running, you will need. Furthermore, Dagster now is a pay-to-use platform.

We wanted to use Dagster but the drawbacks became too big, **we will use Airflow for the orchestrator component.**

Implementation plan

Month 1: Define ETL architecture and Tool selection

Objectives:

- Define an architecture for gathering and consolidating machine learning model metadata from internet platforms in RDF format.
- Select the tools and technologies necessary to build the ETL pipeline Architecture already defined.

Actionable Items:

- **Identify Platforms:** List the specific internet platforms you'll target, considering factors like data quality and coverage, API availability and access terms, etc.
- **Architecture Selection:** Evaluate potential architectures based on:
 - Batch vs. Streaming: Determine if real-time updates are crucial or if periodic batch processing suffices.
 - Microservices vs. Monolithic: Weigh the flexibility and modularity of microservices against the simplicity of a monolithic approach.
 - Initial Load vs. Updates: Plan separate strategies for both, taking into account potential differences in volume, frequency, and complexity.
 - Data Validation and Filtering: Integrate mechanisms to cleanse data, identify errors, and filter out irrelevant information before integration.
 - Data Transformation: Define rules and methods for mapping platform data to your specified metadata schema.
 - Data Storage: Select a suitable storage solution (e.g., Triple Stores, relational database, NoSQL databases, data lakes) based on volume, access patterns, and cost considerations.
 - Error handling and retry mechanisms: Define how to handle errors during data extraction and processing.
- **Architecture representation:** Create diagrams that convey the decisions made.

Deliverables: This document provides a comprehensive Data Pipeline Architecture Design Document capturing all decisions and choices.

Month 2: Access analysis and Technology familiarization.

Objectives:

- Identify how to obtain data from the platforms and what the requirements are for its efficient extraction and transformation.
- Get familiarized with the technologies and tools necessary to implement the ETL pipeline

Actionable Items:

- **Review Platforms Documentation:** Carefully study the documentation provided by each platform, focusing on:
 - Available endpoints and authentication methods.
 - Data formats and structure.
 - Rate limits.
 - API usage costs, if applicable.
- **Test Connectivity:** Build basic scripts or tools to receive data from the platforms and address concerns about them, for example, in case an API is being used, verifying authentication, authorization, and error handling protocols.
- **Model Metadata Schema:** Thoroughly analyze the schema provided by the contractor.
- **Mapping Platform Data to Schema:** Create a detailed mapping document that outlines how data retrieved from each platform maps to the schema's fields and structure.
- **Identify Challenges:** Anticipate and plan for potential difficulties, such as API limitations, inconsistent data formats, or schema changes on the platforms' end.

Deliverables:

- A Github repository documenting how to obtain data from the platforms and the requirements for its efficient extraction and transformation.
- Github repositories with proof of familiarization with the selected tools.

Month 3: Develop Code for Initial Upload and Updates

Objective: Implement the ETL pipeline that gathers, transforms, and stores data according to the defined architecture, tool selection, and data schema.

Actionable Items:

- **Code Structure:** Break down the code into modular components (e.g., data extraction, transformation, loading) for clarity and maintainability.
- **Error Handling:** Incorporate robust error-handling mechanisms to detect and manage issues during data extraction, transformation, and loading.
- **Logging and Monitoring:** Implement logging and monitoring systems to track pipeline activity, identify errors, and ensure data quality.
- **Initial Load:** Create code that efficiently extracts all relevant data from the platforms, transforms it according to the schema, and loads it into the chosen storage system.
- **Update Logic:** Develop logic to handle regular data updates, taking into account:
 - Incremental updates (only extracting what's changed)
 - Full refreshes (periodically reloading all data)
 - Handling deleted or modified data on the platforms
- **Testing and Unit Tests:** Thoroughly test the code components individually and as a whole, covering various scenarios and error conditions.

Readiness levels

Based on the guidelines of [21], we will assign the readiness level that we hope to achieve for the system for each stage of development. For the first month, we want the system to have finished the TRL 1 and TLR 2 stages and be working on the TLR 3 stage. This means that at the end of month 1, we will have formulated our problem, studied the basic principles needed to develop our system, and started doing active research on how to solve the problem and its design.

By the second month, we want to finish the TLR 3 stage and start working on the TLR 4 and TLR 5 stages, which means that we will have finished the system's design and will have proof of concept for different parts of the ETL system, and we will be testing how this different proof of concept interact with each other and with different testing environments.

During the third month, we will have finished TRL stages 4, 5, and 6; the idea is to have a fully functional prototype that can extract data from at least one platform and do the whole ETL pipeline processing. Further TRL stages will be achieved during the remaining months.

Figure 10. Technology Readiness Levels. Source: [23]

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Sources

1. Altexsoft. "The Good and the Bad of Apache Airflow Platform." AltexSoft. Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://www.altexsoft.com/blog/apache-airflow-pros-cons/>.
2. Atlan. "Dagster vs Airflow: Comparing Data Orchestration Capabilities." Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://atlan.com/dagster-vs-airflow/>.
3. ———. "Data Pipeline Architecture: Examples, Best Practices & More!" Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://atlan.com/data-pipeline-architecture/>.
4. Aukstikalnyte, Roberta. "Using Apache Airflow to Build a Pipeline for Scraped Data." Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://oxylabs.io/blog/building-scraping-pipeline-apache-airflow>.
5. Bohorquez, Nicolas. "How to Create Scalable Data Pipelines with Python." *ActiveState* (blog), March 12, 2020. <https://www.activestate.com/blog/how-to-create-scalable-data-pipelines-with-python/>.
6. Crawlbase. "The Perfect Guide to Building a Data Pipeline Architecture | Crawlbase." Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://crawlbase.com/blog/guide-to-data-pipeline-architecture/>.
7. Docker. "Docker Overview." Docker Documentation, 27:26 + +0200 200AD. <https://docs.docker.com/get-started/overview/>.
8. info@bb.agency, BB Agency, and Cody Slingerland. "10 TOP Kubernetes Alternatives In 2024 (Should You Switch?)." CloudZero, January 24, 2024. <https://www.cloudzero.com/blog/kubernetes-alternatives/>.
9. Keboola. "Complete ETL Process Overview (Design, Challenges and Automation)." Accessed February 5, 2024. <https://www.keboola.com/blog/etl-process-overview>.
10. Kiili, Juha. "Modern Web Scraping Pipeline for ML." Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://valohai.com/blog/web-scraping-ml-pipeline/>.
11. Kubernetes. "Kubernetes Overview." Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/>.
12. Lampa, Samuel, Jonathan Alvarsson, and Ola Spjuth. "Towards Agile Large-Scale Predictive Modelling in Drug Discovery with Flow-Based Programming Design Principles." *Journal of Cheminformatics* 8, no. 1 (December 2016): 67. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-016-0179-6>.
13. Machado, Joseph. "Data Pipeline Design Patterns - #1. Data Flow Patterns," December 11, 2022. <https://www.startdataengineering.com/post/design-patterns/>.
14. ———. "Data Pipeline Design Patterns - #2. Coding Patterns in Python," January 12, 2023. <https://www.startdataengineering.com/post/code-patterns/>.
15. Morgan, Patrick. "Python Web Scraping and Data Aggregation Pipelines." Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://www.jpsignum.com/blog/5c6ba462f909a641d754fe79>.
16. NFDI4DS. "NFDI4DS." Accessed February 5, 2024. <https://www.nfdi4datascience.de/>.

17. Prefect. "Welcome to Prefect - Prefect Docs." Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://docs.prefect.io/latest/>.
18. Ryza, Sandy, and Nick Schrock. "Dagster vs. Airflow | Dagster Blog." Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://dagster.io/blog/dagster-airflow>.
19. Slingerland, Cody. "The 11 Best Docker Alternatives (The Complete 2024 List)." CloudZero, October 7, 2022. <https://www.cloudzero.com/blog/docker-alternatives/>.
20. "Python For Data Engineering 2023 Edition," January 9, 2023. <https://www.couponed12.com/2023/01/python-for-data-engineering-2023-edition.htm>.
21. G. Manning, Catherine. "Technology Readiness Levels - NASA," September 27, 2023. <https://www.nasa.gov/directorates/somd/space-communications-navigation-program/technology-readiness-levels/>.
22. Atlassian. "What Is Git | Atlassian Git Tutorial." Atlassian. Accessed February 14, 2024. <https://www.atlassian.com/git/tutorials/what-is-git>.
23. <https://www.lambdatest.com/blog/teamcity-vs-jenkins-picking-the-right-ci-cd-tool>
24. <https://www.lambdatest.com/blog/circleci-vs-travis>
25. <https://www.lambdatest.com/blog/circleci-vs-gitlab>
26. https://huggingface.co/datasets/librarian-bots/model_cards_with_metadata
- 27.